

TECHNICAL JUSTIFICATION OF THE ANTI-DRONE REACTIVE SYSTEM

Egor Andreevich Mikhailov

Original text published in 2023 by Baltic State Technical University

“VOENMEH” named after D.F. Ustinov

Before the start of the special military operation in Ukraine, the feasibility of using small-sized unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs / drones) for military purposes was not so obvious. Despite the first major terrorist act committed using an artisanal UAVs on the night of January 5-6, 2018 at the Khmeimim airbase in Syria, no timely action was taken to prepare means of countering drones. Even in 2018, military correspondents, analysts and competent experts drew attention to the dangerous prospects for the development of small-sized UAVs. Various concepts and technical proposals began to appear that demonstrated the possibilities of using drones for military purposes.

Experts predicted that small-sized UAVs from the "terrorist weapons" class would eventually move into the class of specific military products, joining the ranks of artillery, mortars, missiles, tanks, etc. They also noted the main danger of such drones – the ability to inflict enormous damage with their help, while spending minimal funds. At the moment, both forecasts have been confirmed and do not need to be discussed. Almost any news report from a special military operation area contains the word "drone." The military operation in Ukraine has been dubbed the "Drone War." That is why the issue of countering UAVs is worth special attention.

Work on the proposed system began a year before the special military operation. At that time, the main requirement for the system was formulated: "Destroying UAVs at a reasonable cost." It is worth explaining why this particular requirement was made. The fact is that the "kamikaze drones" used by terrorists in Syria could destroy “SU-35” fighters stationed at the Russian airbase. The planes were saved by repelling the attack with the help of “Pantsir-S1” missiles, and about a dozen rounds of ammunition were spent. And now to the figures: the cost of the

“SU-35” is about 2 billion rubles, the cost of the “Pantsir-S1” missiles is about 60 million rubles apiece, and the estimated cost of the kamikaze drone is no more than 100 thousand rubles. Thus, any use of UAVs/drones causes enormous damage to the defending side. We need a tool that will destroy drones using commensurate resources.

The first step towards solving this problem was to develop a concept for a weapon capable of destroying drones cheaply. A search was conducted for information on examples of effective counteraction to drones. In almost all cases, the following thesis was heard: "It's not a problem to destroy the drone, the problem is to hit it". Then the idea arose to destroy the UAV not with a direct accurate shot, but by creating a fragmentation field in its path, into which it would be shot down.

Hitting air targets by creating a fragmentation field began during the Great Patriotic War (WW2). Large-caliber anti-aircraft guns used fragmentation ammunition with a clockwork mechanism to destroy aircraft. The clockwork mechanism of the fuse was set to the required detonation time, due to the distance to the target. This principle was effective in its own way, but using guns and clockwork mechanisms against drones is impractical.

Modern technical means make it easier and cheaper to implement the corresponding principle of operation. To deliver the destruction system to any point in space, it was decided to use an unguided rocket launcher (URL), in a sense, a "firework". This is due to the absence of the need to use a trunk, which reduces the cost of the complex as a whole. It also makes it possible to simplify the ammunition itself, since the reactive force causes less overload than acceleration in the bore. A timer mounted on electronic components is used to initiate the munition at the right time. As a launcher, it is a structure similar to a firework launcher. The primary images obtained during the development of the concept are shown in Figure 1.

In Figure 1:

Корпус РДТТ – Shell of rocket engine with solid fuel

Заряд РДТТ – Solid fuel of rocket

Шнур самоликвидации – Self-destruct cord

ПДУ – Safety detonating device

Заряд ВВ – Explosives

Корпус ракеты (стальная обечайка) – Rocket shell (steel)

Бортовой разъем – On-board connector

Блок управления – Controller

Дробь – Shots

Figure 1 – The primary forms of the elements of the system under development

Design and analytical activities began with the development of a warhead designed to destroy small-sized UAVs/drones. It was decided to use a fragmentation warhead. A detailed description of the developed mathematical model of an anti-drone warhead is given in the article by Mikhailov E.A., Ivanov V.E. "Calculation of the payload to combat UAVs". The basic idea is a high-density, predictable-shaped fragmentation field that guarantees the destruction of a drone in a given area of space. To reduce the cost and simplify the design, shot is used as fragments, and plastic is used as the body material. TNT was used as the working fluid of the warhead during calculations. The developed mathematical model makes it possible to scale the warhead depending on the task at hand – to change the size of the affected area and the density of the fragmentation field. Figure 2 shows two types of warheads, the first is spherical, creating a fragmentation field in the shape of a ball with a radius of 3 meters, the second is directional. Figure 2 also shows the shapes of the fragmentation fields of the corresponding warheads.

In Figure 2:

- 1 – Spheric warhead
- 2 – Shape of the fragmentation field for spheric warhead at speed of 230 m/s
- 3 – Shape of the fragmentation field for directional warhead at speed of 230 m/s
- 4 – Directional warhead

Figure 2 – Models of warhead shells and corresponding destroying areas

At the next stage, the rocket engine with solid fuel was developed, meeting the requirements of simplicity and cheapness. The calculations were carried out using the “RSI-12K” ballistic fuel. The shape of the filling charge is cylindrical. The working surface is an end face that is flammable on the side of the nozzle block. The front and rear bottoms of the rocket engine with solid fuel are connected to the shell by means of a thread. The material of the solid fuel engine housing is “ST-3”. The thickness of the engine walls is selected in accordance with the operating pressure, axial overloads and engine operating time (heating is calculated to ensure that the housing does not melt). Figure 3 shows a 3D model of the rocket engine.

Figure 3 – Model of solid fuel rocket engine

At the stage of engine development, optimization was carried out using the regular scanning method. The task was to ensure a rocket flight altitude of at least

500 meters when launched at an angle of 85° to the local horizon line. The launch weight of the rocket should not exceed 16 kg. A mathematical model in the form of Excel tables has been created for the engine, which takes into account the overall characteristics of the engine, the second mass flow rate, the expiration rate, the pressure in the combustion chamber, the type of fuel, etc. At the output, the engine thrust and the value of the maximum operating time are obtained. The obtained characteristics were used in a model for constructing a rocket flight path developed in MatLab, which made it possible to choose the best option. Optimal in terms of minimum mass at the specified altitude. Figure 4 shows a fragment of the optimization table and examples of trajectory construction.

Принятое для расчетов давление в камере сгорания, МПа	Наименование топлива	Скорость горения топлива, м/с	Плотность топлива, кг/м ³	Удельный импульс топлива, м/с	Тяга двигателя, Н	Время работы двигателя, сек
29,50	Баллистическое	0,038	1580	2130	644	10,5
28,84		0,038			642	10,6
28,18		0,037			640	10,7
27,53		0,037			638	10,8
26,87		0,037			636	11,0
26,22		0,037			633	11,1
25,58		0,036			630	11,2
24,94		0,036			628	11,3
24,30		0,036			625	11,5
23,66		0,035			622	11,6
23,03		0,035			619	11,8
22,40		0,035			616	11,9
21,77		0,034			613	12,1
21,14		0,034			609	12,2
20,52		0,033			606	12,4
19,91		0,033			602	12,5
19,29		0,033			598	12,7
18,68		0,032			595	12,9
18,07		0,032			591	13,1
17,46		0,032			587	13,3
16,86	0,031	582	13,4			

In Figure 4:

Принятое для расчетов давление в камере сгорания, МПа – Accepted pressure in the combustion chamber for calculations, МПа

Наименование топлива – Name of fuel

Скорость горения топлива, м/с – Burn speed rate of the fuel, m/s

Плотность топлива, кг/м³ – Density of fuel, kg/m³

Удельный импульс топлива, м/с – Specific impulse of fuel, m/s

Тяга двигателя, Н – Engine trust, N

Время работы двигателя, с – Engine working time, s

Высота полета Y, м – Flight altitude Y, m

Траектория полета – Flight trajectory

Дальность полета X, м – Flight range X, m

Figure 4 – The model used to optimize rocket parameters

The instrument compartment is the "storage" of the product's control equipment, the connection between the warhead housings and the solid-fuel rocket engine. In the instrument compartment there is a timer unit on a special nut, a self-destruct cord runs (which lights up only after the engine block is completely burned out, ensuring the initiation of the warhead after a while). The self-destruct cord is designed to ensure that the launched munition self-destructs in the air, in case of non-standard operation of the timer (fuse). Also in the instrument compartment there is a safety detonating device connected to the body of the warhead with a thread. Safety detonating device has an inertial cylinder that stands in a fighting position only under the action of axial inertia. Thus, detonation of the warhead is possible only when the rocket is moving with acceleration (while the engine is running) or from a self-destruct device. The instrument compartment has an on-board connector designed to connect an unguided rocket to a launcher. Figure 5 shows two models of the instrument compartment of the product, which differ in the type of on-board connector.

Figure 5 – Shells of instrument compartment with different types of connectors

It is worth noting that the engine parameters obtained after optimization (thrust, second mass flow, etc.) were used to calculate the geometric parameters of the nozzles. When developing the nozzle block of the product, the main requirement for the design of the ammunition as a whole was taken into account – hitting a given point in space with the smallest deviation. To do this, the ammunition must be statically stable. There are two ways to achieve this: place the rocket's center of pressure behind the center of mass, in the direction of the incoming air flow, or spin the rocket along its own longitudinal axis. As a result, two nozzle block schemes are proposed. The first one has one design nozzle and a tail unit, the second one has a design turbine nozzle. Two products were obtained: an unguided rocket, stabilized by tail, and a turbojet rocket ammunition, stabilized by rotation. A mathematical model has been developed for a turbojet rocket ammunition, which makes it possible to determine the rotation frequency. Also, the design of the warhead has been revised specifically for the turbojet rocket ammunition, with an emphasis on the targeted effect of the damaging factor. In this case, the calculation was carried out by analogy with a spherical warhead. The directional warhead model is shown in Figure 2 pos. 4. Figure 6 shows models of an unguided rocket and a turbojet rocket ammunition, respectively.

In Figure 6:

1 – The turbojet rocket ammunition

2 – Unguided rocket

Figure 6 – Designed ammunitions models

In order to calculate the lead point (the potential meeting point of the UAV and ammunition), you need to predict the trajectory. To predict the trajectory, four parameters are required: the velocity vector of the UAV, coordinates describing its position in space (X, Y, Z). At the time of writing, information has been found in open sources about two UAV detection systems capable of solving this task. Figure 7 shows a general view of these systems and some technical specifications.

In Figure 7:

РЛС «ГЛОБУС» – «The globus» radar station

«РАДЕСКАН-А» – Name of radar system

Надёжная монолитная конструкция без вращающихся элементов – Reliable monolithic construction without rotating parts

Универсальное размещение и интеграция со средствами РЭБ и РТР – Universal placement and integration with electronic warfare and electronic intelligence systems

Высокая дальность и скорость обнаружения без «слепых зон и воронок» – High detection range and speed without "blind spots and craters"

Высокая точность целеуказания для оптического и стрелкового вооружения – High precision targeting for optical and small arms

Низкая стоимость по сравнению с аналогами – Low cost compared to analogues

В поле, на здании, на технике – In the field, on the building, on the equipment

Сферическая зона обнаружения, время обзора 3 секунды – Spherical detection area, 3 seconds viewing time

Распознавания птиц – Идентификация птиц

РЛС – The radar station

ОЭУ – optoelectronic device

ЗУ – anti-aircraft installation

Figure 7 – Radar stations for drones finding

In turn, four parameters are also necessary for the operation of the anti-drone rocket system (launching the ammunitions at the pre-emption point): the launch angle in the horizontal plane, the launch angle in the vertical plane, the launch time and the time of detonation of the warhead. It is assumed that the calculation of these parameters is performed by special software, organized in an electronic computing device. At the same time, the device is located at some distance from the fighting (line of defense), which increases the survivability of the system and reduces the likelihood of destroying the device. Also, the total cost of the complex is reduced, because all control teams are formed in the rear, and only the executive elements of the system are on the front line. A mathematical model has been developed in the MatLab environment that performs the functions of special software. Points are generated according to a given law that simulate the coordinates of drone detection. The time of detection of each point, its coordinates and the speed of movement of the drone are fed to the input of the algorithm. The algorithm predicts the trajectory, calculates potential lead points, and calculates the required launch angles. The launch time is justified by the difference in the flight time of the drone to the lead point and the development ammunition to the lead point. The time of detonation of the warhead depends on the path that ammunition must take to the lead point. Thus, the possibility of implementing such an approach has been proven in practice. Figure 8 shows the results of the program.

In Figure 8:

Координата X, м – Coordinate X, m

Координата Y, м – Coordinate Y, m

Высота полета H, м – Flight altitude H, m

Figure 8 – The results of modeling the functioning of the system (combat interaction) and the corresponding algorithm

A launcher is required to launch the ammunition. It should ensure the safety of the product, the required launch angles, and the shortest possible reaction time. Maximum simplicity and low cost should also be ensured. A model of a launcher similar to a firework launcher has been developed. Launching tubes are used to place rockets, which increases the safety of ammunition. The variability of the launch angles is provided in both the horizontal and vertical planes. At the same time, it is possible to launch several ammunition at different angles at once, which allows you to simultaneously "close" different areas of space. It is assumed that the munition is

connected to the launcher via a wire with a plug, which transmits the time of detonation of the warhead to the timer. The wire provides reusable use, as the connector disconnects at startup, rather than the cable breaks. The ammunition engine is started by a flare from the launcher, which reduces the cost of the "consumable resource" - designed ammunition. The launcher is equipped with sensors for temperature, wind speed, pressure, humidity, which allows you to adjust the launch conditions because the parameters of the operation of a solid-fuel rocket engine depend on the parameters of the external environment. The launcher can be connected to the control unit via radio or by wire. The dimensions and weight of the launcher allow it to be placed in the body, for example, UAZ Pickup or UAZ Cargo. At the same time, one person is enough to maintain and recharge the battery. Figure 9 shows images of the launcher model.

Figure 9 – Designed launchers model with different launch angles

A model for choosing the optimal aiming point has been developed. Which allows, if possible, to destroy several drones with one shot. This model is at the conceptual stage and needs to be refined to a three-dimensional one. The algorithm is as follows: the radius of the warhead damage zone is set during detonation, and special distances are calculated for known drone coordinates on the plane (in this case, randomly generated ones). If the radius/diameter of the affected area exceeds these distances, the algorithm outputs the coordinates of the aiming point, upon hitting which the munition will destroy several drones. The algorithm allows you to analyze from 1 to 5 drones at the discretion of the user. Figure 10 shows the results

of the program. It is worth noting that the scope of this algorithm is not limited to aiming at drones, but with the right approach can be used in a different direction.

Figure 10 – Examples working of optimal choosing aim point program

A model has been developed that allows choosing the optimal layout of launchers at the line of defense. It is assumed that the probability of destroying a drone depends only on the distance between the lead point and the location of the launcher. For the developed system, the coverage area can be approximated by a cylinder with a height of 500 meters and a base diameter of 400 meters. Where the center of the cylinder base is the launcher location. Then, for a certain height, the coverage area is a circle divided into sectors, where each sector corresponds to a certain probability of destroying the UAV.

With this approach, it is possible to determine the probability of destroying a drone moving through the defense line. The trajectory of the drone is approximated by a straight line. If the line (trajectory) intersects any circle, the algorithm calculates the probability of hitting the UAV for this circle. The value corresponding to the highest probability of destruction is selected (within one circle, the trajectory can pass through several sectors, in which case the probability of destruction corresponds to the largest of the intersected sectors). If the trajectory of the drone passes through several circles (over several launchers), then the final probability of damage is calculated using the formula:

$$P_y = 1 - (1 - P_1) * (1 - P_2) * ... * (1 - P_i)$$

Where P_y is the probability of destroying the drone when passing through the border, P_i is the probability of destroying the drone on a single launcher.

The model allows the user to select the number of launchers, the radius of the coverage area, the number of sectors, the size of sectors, and the probability of drone destruction in sectors. The user places the launchers on the coordinate plane, choosing different placement schemes. The trajectory of the drone passing through the defense line is randomly generated. The probability of destroying a drone moving along the generated trajectory is calculated. Then the simulation is repeated a large number of times (set by the user). As a result, an estimate of the mathematical expectation of the probability of destroying a drone at the turn is calculated. The developed model demonstrates a method for solving similar problems and needs further analysis and elaboration. Figure 11 shows examples of the program's results.

Figure 11 – The results of statistical modeling of some boundary alignment schemes

A model has been created for the scattering of UAV debris as a result of successful combat use. The location of the objects at the time of detonation, the initial velocities of both objects, the angle of approach of the ammunition to the drone and the force of the shock wave from the action of the warhead of the projectile are taken into account. A set of drone fragments is randomly generated, while the sum of the masses of the fragments does not exceed the mass of the whole drone. The number of rocket fragments is also randomly generated. Drag coefficients characteristic of bodies of various geometric shapes are randomly selected from a given array. A random factor is introduced that affects the angle of debris spread. This model allows you to estimate where the debris that may pose a danger will fall.

With such a model, with further research, it is possible to more reasonably substantiate one or another scheme of boundary alignment. Figure 12 shows examples of simulation results for debris scattering.

Figure 12 - Trajectories of the UAV debris

The developed system is a technical proposal for a small UAV counteraction system. At the current stage, there remains a detailed study by experts of individual parts of the complex, since it is impossible to take into account all the nuances in all areas as a student. We can also say that this system has the right to life and will work as intended. It remains to be hoped that in the future it will be possible to implement this system "in metal".

Bibliographic list:

1. Explosives: textbook / Yu.V. Genkin; Baltic State Technical University. University of St. Petersburg, 2007– 114 p.
2. The effectiveness of missile systems: a method. instructions for the lab. works / S.N. Yeltsin; Baltic State Technical University. University of St. Petersburg, 2011– 74 p.
3. Fundamentals of the design and calculation of artillery ammunition: a textbook / E.A. Znamensky; Baltic State Technical University. University of St. Petersburg, 2016. 57 p.

4. Handbook of Explosives, 2009 // Access mode: <https://studizba.com/files/show/pdf/61426-1-spravochnik-po-vv-i-pirosostavam-.html> (date of request: 04.01.2022)
5. "Shot down a quadcopter with a shotgun." [video recording] // YouTube. Access mode: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Zjmz0buBass> (date of request: 08.12.2021)
6. "Shooting at drones." [video recording] // YouTube. Access mode: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jj79bZbDAzs> (date of request: 09.12.2021)
7. Pour on Khmeimim: <https://centercigr.livejournal.com/80961.html> (date of request: 11/23/2021)
8. Engineering problems of rocket design: a textbook / A.L. Isakov; Baltic State Technical University. University of St. Petersburg, 2017– 113 p.
9. Fundamentals of theory and design of solid fuel rocket engines: a textbook / V.I. Baloban; Baltic State Technical University. University of St. Petersburg, 2005– 139 p.
10. Rocket fuels / V.K. Ponomarenko; A.F. Mozhaisky WICCA – SPb., 1995. – 619 p.
11. A package of applied CAD programs for BR and RN spacecraft: a textbook / A.L.Isakov; Baltic State Technical University. University of St. Petersburg, 2014. – 100 p.
12. Synthesis of the BR image: a textbook / A.L.Isakov; Baltic State Technical University. University of St. Petersburg, 2010. 128 p.
13. Fuels and working bodies of rocket engines: a textbook for aviation universities / M.S.Shteher; "Mechanical Engineering", 1976. – 304 p.
14. Handbook of hydraulic resistances / I.E.Idelchik / Edited by M.O.Steinberg – 3rd ed. and add. – M.: "Mechanical Engineering", 1992. – 672 p.
15. Tables of gas dynamic functions: a reference manual / F.I.Luhtura, Mariupol State Technical University, 2007. 152 p.
16. Rocket engines with combined fuel / E.B.Volkov, G.Y.Mazing, Yu.N.Shishkin; "Mashinostroenie", Moscow, 1973. 180 p.

17. Energy condensed systems: a short encyclopedic dictionary / Edited by B.P.Zhukov. 2nd Ed., corrected. – M.: Janus-K, 2000. – 596 p.

18. Manual on the study of unguided missiles / Yu.V.Gomzin; MV and MTR of the USSR Leningrad Order of the Red Banner Mechanical Institute, Leningrad, 1973. 73 p.

19. The device and functioning of the guided anti-aircraft missile 9M331 "Tor-M1": A textbook / S.N.Yeltsin; Baltic State Technical University. University of St. Petersburg, 2005. 54 p.

20. UAV flight dynamics: a textbook for universities / A.A.Lebedev, L.S.Chernobrovkin; M., "Mechanical Engineering", 1973, 616 p.

21. Intracameral processes in solid fuel rocket engines: a textbook / V.P.Below; Baltic State Technical University. University of St. Petersburg, 2018, 56 p.

22. Trajectory tasks in the dynamics of aircraft movement: a practical guide / T.Y.Lemeshonok, A.A.Sizova; Baltic State University. Technical University of St. Petersburg, 2021, 76 p.

23. Patent application "RU 2189371 C1" - the rate of combustion of ballistic fuels, 2002 // Gorenje: https://yandex.ru/patents/doc/RU2189371C1_20020920 (date of request: 05/13/2022)

24. The device and the basics of operation of the Pantsir-S missile defense system (general information): textbook / Yu.P.Samokhvalov, Yu.F.Kupriyanov, S.V.Luppey; edited by N.P.Timofeev; Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Russian Federation, Ural Federal University. Yekaterinburg: Ural Publishing House. University, 2021. 123 p.

25. Handbook of Materials, 2022 // Access mode: <https://tehtab.ru/Guide/GuideMatherials> / (date of access: 05/14/2022)

26. RADEKSCAN-A drone detection station, 2022 // Access mode: https://umirs.ru/catalog/stationary_complex/kort-radeskan-a / (date of request: 15.01.2023)

27. RADAR "GLOBUS", 2022 // Access mode: http://zavant.ru/Video/радар_Глобус.pdf (date of access: 01/15/2023)

28. About drones in the SVR, 2023 // Access mode:
<https://news.ru/society/vojna-bespilotnikov> / (date of access: 02/04/2023)
29. UAV in SVO, 2022 // Access mode:
<https://www.kp.ru/daily/27417/4616799> / (date of request: 02/04/2023)
30. Large-caliber anti-aircraft guns, 2021 // Access mode:
<https://topwar.ru/181934-ispolzovanie-trofejnyh-nemeckih-105-i-128-mm-zenitnyh-orudij.html> (accessed 02/01/2023)